

THE FEATURES OF THE USAGE OF TRUNCATIONS IN THE ENGLISH-LANGUAGE PRESS

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Despite the in-depth study, the texts of newspapers and magazines are still worthy material for linguistic observations. The press, reflecting the fixed form of language in writing, continues to remain a reliable means of storage and dissemination of key linguistic trends. In the press, the formation of the main stylistic techniques and tools used today in media texts in general took place. The research material was 13,028 examples of the use of abbreviations in the British and American press.

Keywords: press, linguistics, mass media, truncation, style.

Introduction. In the linguistic life of modern society, mass media are gaining more and more importance. At the beginning of the 21st century, we are witnessing the most intensive development of society's speech practice in mass media (mass media). The volume of information that is processed daily is rapidly increasing, which, in turn, provokes a complex arrangement of the language structure of mass media, a deepening of the stylistic differentiation of texts, and a change in the public consciousness of the status of information products. Mass media are often assigned the role of "the main language tutor after school" [1].

Despite the in-depth study, the texts of newspapers and magazines are still worthy material for linguistic observations. The press, reflecting the fixed form of language in writing, continues to remain a reliable means of storage and dissemination of key linguistic trends. Moreover, in our opinion, the role of the basic component in a number of existing mass media can be legitimately assigned to the press, since it was here that the formation of the main stylistic techniques and tools used today in media texts in general took place. This is the reason for our appeal to the materials of the modern British and American press, on the basis of which it is possible to productively study the linguistic phenomena characteristic of the English language of the 21st century.

At the current stage of development, the English language is characterized by a surge of interest in various abbreviations, truncations occupy a special place among them. And although the creation of truncations is a natural tendency that has been characteristic of English for many centuries, it is now that this link of the lexical system is being activated. Some words created with the help of truncation have become the basic, most frequent and significant words of our time.

Research materials and methods. The research material was 13,028 examples of the use of abbreviations in the British and American press. The sources for the selection of shortened units were the following publications: quality newspapers and magazines ("The Independent", "The International Herald Tribune", "BusinessWeek", "Forbes", "Newsweek", "The Economist", "The Daily Telegraph", "The Times"), mass press ("New York Post", "New York Times", "The Sun", "USA Today", "Daily Mail", "Daily Mirror", "Daily

News"), tabloid entertainment publications ("The National Enquirer", "People", "OK", "Hello!", "Closer", "Hot Stars", "Love it!"), youth publications ("Bliss", "Sugar", "LadMag", "Cosmopolitan", "Glamour"). The involvement of diverse publications in terms of content, style and target dominance allows us to trace the patterns of the use of truncations taking into account the social differentiation of the language, and even to fully reveal both the general and specific features of the studied phenomenon.

The **purpose of the study** is to determine the place of truncations in the lexical arsenal of the English-language press, to identify and systematize the units that are most actively used, and to establish their functional and pragmatic originality.

Mass media are designed to reflect and accumulate public opinion, forming criteria for evaluating the events taking place, and thus influencing the behavior and views of individuals and the entire society as a whole.

However, the mass media play an important role not only in the social, but also in the linguistic life of society, being a specially organized infrastructure that records language changes at a certain stage of development. Nowhere, in our opinion, is there such a close "contact" of language with the life of society as in mass media. So, practically everything related to the problems of language as a phenomenon is manifested in the most profound and, perhaps, vivid form in the language of mass media. Mass media texts, reflecting various aspects of life, to a greater or lesser extent reflect various realizations of the national language, conveying a synchronous "slice" of the language state. N. Avetisyan's opinion is justified in that language is also a mirror of society, therefore the language of means is a litmus test of the state of the language itself [2].

Analysis of the linguistic literature of different years shows that the absolute majority of researchers also qualify the language of mass media as a sphere of active language processes [4; 9].

The mass media are the most susceptible to the processes taking place in the language: all "innovations" are quickly recorded in the press, on television, radio and the Internet, and then - either fixed in the language as a norm, or "separated" by the language collective and remain occasional. This allows us to assume

that a kind of movement, the evolution of language means is carried out through the media: "The mass media (print, radio, television, Internet), being a collective subject, use different language means, being the main engine of the variability of the language picture of the world" [6].

The Internet, television, radio, and the press are direct recorders of language transformations of the beginning of the 21st century. It is in these spheres that the key trends in the development of the language of the modern era are fixed and receive their final design. This determines the natural interest of linguists in mass media texts. In recent years, it is even appropriate to talk about the development of a whole direction in linguistics, which is being developed at the intersection of many sciences - media linguistics, the subject of which is the language of mass media. This is one of the most active and developing academic disciplines, within which a systematic, comprehensive study of the language of the mass media and its functioning in the field of mass communication is carried out, various methodological principles are developed, as well as a terminological apparatus for researching the parameters of the description of mass media texts.

It is especially relevant for us to study the language of mass media of the English-speaking world, which is rightly recognized as the "highway" of the evolution of modern media. In particular, the mass media of Great Britain and the USA, possessing the most powerful financial support, as well as high technical potential, currently dictate media standards, which are later adopted by journalists from other countries. According to various sources, from 60 to 90% of information in the whole world is in English. And this means that the key language trends in the mass media industry, the tone and character of the design and presentation of information are also spread by the English-language media.

It must be stated that the interest of researchers in the field of media language is mainly attracted by the language of periodicals. This state of affairs is explained by the fact that newspaper and magazine journalism is often given a special status, emphasizing its primacy and, therefore, priority in relation to other mass media [4]. Moreover, achievements in the field of newspaper and journalistic style research are, in a certain sense, the theoretical basis for the development of media linguistics.

In our work, we will also limit ourselves to the framework of English-language newspaper and magazine texts, promoting the press to the position of the most significant and significant of all existing mass media.

The rapid pace of development of society, as well as the progressive complication of the structure of means, contribute to a change in the appearance of the press. Along with these changes, the requirements for the periodical vary, and some of its functions are adjusted. However, the most important, essential characteristics of the press, its standards come from the basic features of journalism as a functional style and remain stable for a considerable period. In view of the rather in-depth study of the functional and stylistic specifics of the press, we will limit ourselves to a quick review of its constitutive parameters.

The differential features of newspaper and magazine texts are closely related to the main functions of the press as a component of journalistic style. As the analysis revealed, the tradition of distinguishing the functions of periodicals can be traced in many works [6; 9]. Eliminating some differences in wording, the set of functions of periodicals mentioned in the linguistic literature can be reduced to the following components: 1) informative; 2) valid; 3) expressive; 4) educational; 5) educational; 6) organizational; 7) entertaining; 8) attractive.

The functions of informing and influencing are traditionally considered the most "recognized" from the point of view of styling. The language of the press is a kind of "moving language continuum that exists as if between two main poles: the function of the message and the function of influence" [2; 8]. The correlation between these two sides can vary depending on the target setting of the text, but most often the message and impact functions are applied simultaneously.

The constructive principles of the organization of language means - the principles of standard and expression - are correlated with the specified functions. Orientation to the standard is caused by the newspaper's appeal to a large and diverse audience and is manifested in the choice of easily reproduced lexical units with unambiguous semantics and a neutral-normative color. The need to focus on the addressee is related to "overcoming the stereotype" and consists in the development of special forms of expression.

The specificity of the language of the press is most often considered from the point of view of the presence in its texts of linguistic units of different functional styles: "The language of mass communication texts is stylistically heterogeneous, syncretic in terms of the use of oral and written forms of language, it is characterized by interpenetration of styles and blurring of units" [2; 7].

Thus, summarizing the experience of various researchers in the field of the language of the modern press, it can be stated that the following features are observed in the language structure of newspapers and magazines:

- 1) widespread use of media influence techniques in the press;
- 2) the conciseness of the presentation, due to the law of saving time and printed space;
- 3) significant democratization of style;
- 4) "patterning" of texts, simplification of their structure;
- 5) significant "personification", i.e. strengthening of the subjective beginning in coverage of events;
- 6) deepening genre and species hybridization;
- 7) reducing the amount of factual information due to the priority of the stylistic design of the text;
- 8) strengthening of the beginning of the game and the so-called "precedence" (especially in the titles);
- 9) tangible "ironic flavor" of published materials;
- 10) expansion of the volume of the lexical base due to the transfer to the center of the language system of elements of peripheral spheres (colloquial language, professional jargon, slang);
- 11) a variety of phraseological units, stable phrases, neologisms, idioms, various abbreviations, joining words with the help of dashes and others.

One of the most general factors determining the high concentration of abbreviations in the press is, in our opinion, the tendency to use fashionable, socially prestigious language forms and expressions. Due to their greater relevance, truncations can be perceived as more prestigious and modern than their expanded prototypes. Abbreviations to some extent convey the flavor of our time: shortening words is a natural process in the conditions of the rapid development of technical means and the huge amount of information that comes in every day.

During the analysis of abbreviations in newspapers and magazines, we discovered the following pattern: the saturation of texts with "fashionable" abbreviations is to a greater extent characteristic of the women's press. Women's magazines "Cosmopolitan", "Glamour" or publications for teenage girls "Bliss", "Sugar" are distinguished by the regular reproduction in the language of truncated forms of words. Up to 300 or more units created according to the truncation model can be used in one issue of such a publication. Among the most popular abbreviations, the following should be noted: fab (fabulous), comfy (comfortable), combo (combination), prob (problem), tude (attitude), convo (conversation), delish (delicious), glam (glamorous), gorge (gorgeous), etc. Here are some examples:

A secret language with your guy makes everyday convo spicy [11].

Especially "fashionable" in the women's press are adjectives of the highest degree of evaluation - fab, gorge, glam, delish. According to our observations, the most frequent unit of this series is the truncation fab. Originating in the early 60s of the 20th century, it owes its popularity to the famous youth vocal-instrumental ensemble "The Beatles" (the so-called "The Fab Four"). Currently, this reduction is experiencing a "second birth" to some extent. The attractiveness of this word form, in our opinion, lies in its semantic "uncertainty", which means that it can be used in the vast majority of cases to describe the "amazing" qualities of objects or phenomena (e.g. fab shoes, fab party, fab life, fab products, fab weekend, fab treat, fab freckles, look-fab, feel fab beauty, etc.).

The quantitative advantage of truncations in the women's press is probably explained by the fact that women, to a greater extent than men, tend to use language forms that are prestigious in society - many linguists have drawn attention to this at different times. Thus, E. Yesina, reflecting on the reasons for the particular popularity of abbreviations in the women's press, concludes that women less than others want to lag behind fashionable language trends, and therefore actively support the tendency to use abbreviated units.

Thus, the use of abbreviations on the pages of the press can be considered as a reflection of a fashionable language manner that helps to create and maintain the "prestige" of newspapers and magazines, to give the reader the impression of "progressiveness", the ability to keep up with the times. Striving for innovation in the language has its positive sides - it affects the formation of literary norms, ensures a constant change of the lexical repertoire and thereby contributes to the enrichment of the language. In other words, this is a kind of evidence of the life of the language.

Today, dynamic linguistic processes are taking place in the English language, one of which is the formation and functioning of abbreviations. Their spread reflects the modern direction of the development of the English language, which is characterized, on the one hand, by an emphasis on compression, and, on the other hand, by a high level of looseness of language relations, a desire for freshness of word usage, constant renewal of linguistic means, a deliberate emphasis on changes in value orientations, a weakening of stylistic "censor" and active assimilation of peripheral elements.

The conducted research made it possible to offer a more refined idea of the nature of this linguistic phenomenon, as well as to expand existing concepts about the sphere of functioning of truncations. Traditionally, belonging to the environment of "marginal" phenomena of the English language and being outside the officially accepted language canons, abbreviations persistently penetrate the pages of newspapers and magazines, and then - into the widely used vocabulary. Under certain conditions, abbreviations become part of the literary language.

Conclusions. Mass media play a key role in the evolution of language, contributing to the redistribution of the lexical composition and the expansion of the boundaries of the literary norm. The mass media are the first to record and introduce new phenomena, concepts, and words into a wide field of use. This proves the importance of our approach to the texts of newspapers and magazines as a worthy material for studying such units that are relevant for English today as truncation.

References

1. Селіванова О. О. Сучасна лінгвістика: напрями та проблеми. Полтава : Довкілля, 2008. 712 с. 66
2. Alexander J. D. Aphesis in English. N.Y., 1988. Vol. 39, № 1. P. 29-65.
3. The American magazine: research, perspectives and prospects / ed. by D. Abrahamson. Ames, Iowa: Iowa State University Press, 1995. 240 p.
4. Bell A. The Language of the News Media. Oxford : Blackwell, 1991. 277 p.
5. Bogart L. Preserving the press: how daily newspapers mobilized to keep their readers. New York : Columbia University Press, 1991. 327 p.
6. Halliday M. A. K. The Linguistic Sciences and Language Teaching. London, 1965. 77 p.
7. Hoggart R. Mass media in a mass society: myth and reality. London: Continuum, 2004. 214 p.
8. Leech G. N. Principles of Pragmatics. London and New York, 1983. 250 p.
9. Media and Cultural regulation. Open univ., 1997. 248 p.
10. Marchand H. The Categories and Types of Present-Day English Word-Formation. A Synchronic-diachronic approach. Alabama: University of Alabama Press, 1966. 380 p.
11. Soudek L. Structure of Substandard Words in British and American English. Bratislava, 1967. 232 p.
12. Stevenson R. L. Global communication in the twenty-first century. New York : Longman, 1994. 382p.